

EKSTREMUMNING ZARURIY SHARTI

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ANNOTATSIYA.

Funksiya hosilalari yordamida uning ekstremum nuqtalarini topish osonlashadi.

Ushbu maqolada shu masala ko’rilgan va yechish yo’llari misollar yordamida ko’rsatilgan.

Kalit so’zlar: Statsionar, Ekstremum, kritik, teorema, uzluksiz, maksimum.

Avval ekstremumning zaruriy shartini ifodalovchi teoremani keltiramiz.

Teorema. Agar $f(x)$ funksiya x_0 nuqtada uzluksiz, shu nuqtada ekstremumga ega bo’lsa, u holda bu nuqtada $f(x)$ funksiyaning hosilasi nolga teng yoki mavjud emas.

Isboti. Faraz qilaylik $f(x)$ funksiya x_0 nuqtada maksimumga ega bo’lsin. U holda x_0 nuqtaning shunday $(x_0-d; x_0+d)$ atrofi mavjud bo’lib, bu atrofdan olingan "x

uchun $f(x_0) > f(x)$ bo’ladi. Agar $x > x_0$ bo’lsa, u holda $\frac{f(x) - f(x_0)}{x - x_0} < 0$ tengsizlik,

agar $x < x_0$ bo’lsa, u holda $\frac{f(x) - f(x_0)}{x - x_0} > 0$ tengsizlik o’rinli bo’lishi ravshan.

Bu tengsizliklar chap tomonidagi ifodalarning $x \rightarrow x_0$ da limiti mavjud bo’lsa, u holda

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0+0} \frac{f(x) - f(x_0)}{x - x_0} = f'(x_0+0) \neq 0, \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0-0} \frac{f(x) - f(x_0)}{x - x_0} = f'(x_0-0) \neq 0 \text{ bo'ladi.}$$

Agar funksiyaning chap $f'(x_0-0)$ va o’ng $f'(x_0+0)$ hosilalari nolga teng bo’lsa, u holda funksiya hosilasi $f'(x_0)$ mavjud va nolga teng bo’ladi.

Agar $f'(x_0-0)$ va $f'(x_0+0)$ lar noldan farqli bo’lsa, ravshanki $f'(x_0+0) < f'(x_0-0)$ bo’lib, $f'(x_0)$ mavjud bo’lmaydi.

Funksiya x_0 nuqtada minimumga ega bo’lgan hol ham yuqoridagi kabi isbotlanadi. Teorema isbot bo’ldi.

1-misol. Ma’lumki, $f(x) = |x|$ funksiyaning $x=0$ da hosilasi mavjud emas. Bu funksiya $x=0$ nuqtada minimumga ega.

2-misol. $f(x) = \sqrt[3]{x^2}$ bo'lsin.

2-chizma

$$f'(-0) = \lim_{x \rightarrow -0} \frac{\sqrt[3]{x^2}}{x} = \lim_{x \rightarrow -0} \frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{x^2}} = -\infty, \quad f'(+0) = \lim_{x \rightarrow +0} \frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{x^2}} = +\infty$$

bo'lgani uchun $x=0$

nuqtada funksiyaning ham hosilasi mavjud emas. Ammo bu funksiya $x=0$ nuqtada minimumga ega bo'lishi ravshandir. (2- chizma)

Ta'rif. Funksiya hosilasini nolga aylantiradigan nuqtalar yoki hosila mavjud bo'lmaydigan nuqtalar funksiyaning **kritik nuqtalari** deb ataladi. Funksiya hosilasi nolga teng bo'lgan nuqtalar **statsionar nuqtalar** deb ataladi.

Har qanday kritik nuqta funksiyaning ekstremal nuqtasi bo'lavermaydi.

Masalan: $f(x)=(x-1)^3$, $f'(x)=3(x-1)^2$, $f'(1)=0$ bo'lib, $x_0=1$ kritik nuqta. Lekin $x_0=1$ nuqtaning ixtiyoriy atrofida $f(1)=0$ eng kichik, yoki eng katta qiymat bo'la olmaydi. Chunki har bir atrofda noldan kichik va noldan katta qiymatlar istalgancha bor.

Demak, $f(x)$ funksiyaga ekstremum qiymat beruvchi nuqtalarni funksiyaning statsionar nuqtalari, funksiyaning hosilasi mavjud bo'lmagan nuqtalar, funksiyaning hosilasi cheksiz bo'lgan nuqtalar orasidan izlash kerak ekan. Odatda bunday nuqtalar ekstremumga **shubhali nuqtalar** deyiladi.

Quyida funksiya grafitinging kritik nuqta atrofidagi holatlari tasvirlangan (3- chizma).

Teorema. Faraz qilaylik $f(x)$ funksiya x_0 nuqtada uzluksiz va x_0 nuqta funksiyaning kritik nuqtasi bo'lsin.

a) Agar " $x \in (x_0-d; x_0)$ " uchun $f'(x) > 0$, " $x \in (x_0; x_0+d)$ " uchun

$f'(x) < 0$ tengsizliklar o'rinli bo'lsa, ya'ni $f'(x)$ hosila x_0 nuqtadan o'tishida o'z ishorasini «+» dan «-» ga o'zgartirsa, u holda $f(x)$ funksiya x_0 nuqtada maksimumga ega bo'ladi.

b) Agar " $x \in (x_0-d; x_0)$ " uchun $f'(x) < 0$, " $x \in (x_0; x_0+d)$ " uchun $f'(x) > 0$ tengsizliklar o'rinli bo'lsa, ya'ni $f'(x)$ hosila x_0 nuqtadan o'tishda o'z ishorasini «-» dan «+» ga

o'zgartirsa, u holda $f(x)$ funksiya x_0 nuqtada minimumga ega bo'ladi.

c) Agar $f'(x)$ hosila x_0 nuqtadan o'tishda o'z ishorasini o'zgartirmasa, u holda $f(x)$ funksiya x_0 nuqtada ekstremumga ega bo'lmaydi.

Isbot. a) Holni qaraymiz. Bu holda " $x \in (x_0-d; x_0)$ " uchun $f'(x) > 0$ bo'lishidan $f(x)$ funksiyaning $(x_0-d; x_0)$ da qat'iy o'suvchiligi kelib chiqadi. So'ngra shartga ko'ra $f(x)$ funksiya x_0 nuqtada uzluksiz bo'lgani sababli

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0-0} f(x) = \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0+0} f(x) = f(x_0) \quad (1)$$

tenglik o'rinli. Demak, " $x \in (x_0-d; x_0)$ " uchun

$$f(x) < f(x_0) \quad (2)$$

bo'ladi. " $x \in (x_0; x_0+d)$ " uchun $f'(x) < 0$ bo'lishidan $f(x)$ funksiyaning $(x_0; x_0+d)$ da qat'iy kamayuvchiligi kelib chiqadi. Demak, (1) tenglikni e'tiborga olsak, " $x \in (x_0; x_0+d)$ " uchun yana (2) tengsizlik bajariladi. Bundan " $x \in (x_0-d; x_0+d)$ " uchun $f(x) < f(x_0)$ bo'ladi, ya'ni $f(x)$ funksiya x_0 nuqtada maksimumga ega.

b) Bu holda $f(x)$ funksiya x_0 nuqtada minimumga erishishi (a) holga o'xshash isbotlanadi.

$f'(x)$ hosila x_0 nuqtadan o'tishda o'z ishorasini o'zgartirmaydigan (c) holda $f(x)$ funksiya x_0 nuqtaning $(x_0-d; x_0+d)$ atrofida qat'iy o'suvchi yoki qat'iy kamayuvchi bo'ladi. Demak, x_0 nuqtada yo'q.

Demak funksiyaning ekstremumini topishda funksiya hosilasi ishorasining o'zgarishi, ekstremum mavjudligining yetarli sharti bo'lib, zaruriy sharti emas bo'la olmas ekan.

Eslatma. Yuqoridagi mulohazalarda $f(x)$ funksiya x_0 nuqtada uzluksiz bo'lishi muhim. Masalan, ushbu

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x^4, & \text{agar } x \neq 0, \\ 1, & \text{agar } x = 0 \end{cases}$$
 funksiyani qaraylik. Bu funksiya uchun $f'(x) = 4x^3$ bo'lib, hosila $x=0$ nuqtadan o'tishda o'z ishorasini «-» dan «+» ga o'zgartirsa ham, berilgan funksiya $x=0$ nuqtada minimumga ega emas.

Eslatma. x_0 nuqtaning chap tomonidan o'ng tomoniga o'tganda hosila ishorasini o'zgartirmasa ham bu nuqta funksiyaning ekstremum nuqtasi bo'lishi mumkin.

Masalan,
$$f(x) = \begin{cases} -x, & x \leq 1, \\ 2-x, & x > 1 \end{cases}$$
 funksiya uchun $x=1$ (minimum) nuqta bo'ladi. Haqiqatdan, $x=1$ ning $(0;2)$ atrofidagi barcha nuqtalar uchun $f(x)^3 f(1) = -1$ tengsizlik o'rini bo'ladi. Shu bilan birga $x < 1$ va $x > 1$ nuqtalar uchun $f'(x) = -1 < 0$, ya'ni hosila ishorasini o'zgartirmaydi.

$y = f(x)$ funksiya uchun ekstremum qiymat beruvchi nuqtalarni birinchi tartibli hosila yordamida tekshirish qoidasi:

1. $f'(x)$ hosila topiladi.
2. $y = f(x)$ funksiyaning kritik nuqtalari, ya'ni $f'(x) = 0$ hosila nolga aylanadigan yoki uzilishga ega bo'lgan nuqtalar topiladi.
3. Topilgan kritik nuqtalar $f(x)$ funksiyaning aniqlanish sohasini oraliqlarga ajratadi, shu oraliqlarda $f'(x)$ hosilaning ishorasi tekshiriladi.
4. Funksiyaning ekstremum nuqtalardagi qiymatlari hisoblanadi.

1-misol. $y = 2x^3 - 6x^2 - 48x - 17$

Funksiyaning ekstremum qiymatlarini toping.

Yechish. Ushbu funksiyaning ekstremum qiymatlarini topamiz buning uchun.

a) funksiya hosila olamiz

$$y' = 6x^2 - 12x - 48 \quad y' = 6x^2 - 12x - 48 \text{ ga ega bo'lamiz}$$

b) kritik nuqtalarini topamiz.

$$6x^2 - 12x - 48 = 0 \quad 6x^2 - 12x - 48 = 0 \quad \div 6 \div 6$$

$$x^2 - 2x - 8 = 0 \quad x^2 - 2x - 8 = 0 \quad x_1 = -2 \quad x_2 = 4$$

c) Endi ushbu kritik nuqtalarni ishorasini tekshiramiz.

“+” dan “-” ga o'tgani uchun $x = -2$ maksimum nuqta

“-” dan “+” ga o'tgani uchun $x = 4$ minimum nuqta

d) ekstremal qiymatlarni toppish uchun topilgan ekstremal nuqtalarni funksiyaga etib qo'yamiz.

Bunda

$$y(-2) = 41 \quad y(4) = -177$$

Demak $y_{\max} = 41$ $y_{\min} = -177$ ga ega bo'lamiz.

Masala. Moddiy nuqta $S(t) = 12t^2 - \frac{2}{3}t^3$ qonunga

binoan to'g'ri chiziq bo'ylab harakat qilmoqda, bunda $S(t)$ metr larda hisoblangan vaqt. $[4; 10]$

Oraliqqa tegishli qanday vaqt paytida nuqta harakatining tezligi eng katta bo'ladi va bu tezlik qanday kattalikda bo'ladi?

Yechish. Biz bilamizki yo'ldan olingan hosila tezlikni, tezlikdan olingan hosila esa tezlanishni beradi. Shu sababli berilgan harakat tenglamasidan hosila olamiz.

$$s'(t) = v(t) = 24t - 2t^2$$

$$v(t) = 24t - 2t^2$$

Ushbu tezlik tenglamasidan hosila olib, nolga tenglashtirsak kritik nuqtaga ega bo'lamiz.

$v'(t) = 0$ $24 - 4t = 0$ $t = 6$ bu nuqta bizga berilgan oraliqda bor.

Endi $t = 6$ da va oraliqning chetki nuqtalaridagi tezlikning qiymatlarini topamiz va ular ichidan eng kattasini yechim sifatida olamiz. Chunki masala shartida tezligi eng katta bo'lishi kerakligi talab qilingan

$$v(6) = 72 \quad v(4) = 64 \quad v(10) = 40$$

Tezlik eng katta bo'ladigan vaqt $t = 6$ da ekan.

Misol. $y = \frac{x^2}{x-2}$ funksiyani ekstremumlarini toping.

Yechish. Avvalo ushbu funksiyadan hosila olib, nolga tenglashtirib, kritik nuqtalarni topib olamiz.

$$y' = \frac{2x(x-2) - x^2}{(x-2)^2} = \frac{x^2 - 4x}{(x-2)^2} = \frac{x(x-4)}{(x-2)^2}$$

$$\frac{x(x-4)}{(x-2)^2} = 0$$

$x = 0$ $x = 4$ $x = 2$ kritik nuqtalarni funksiya hosilasidagi ishorasini tekshiramiz.

Tekshirganimizda $x_{max} = 0$ $x_{min} = 4$ $x_{max} = 0$ $x_{min} = 4$ bo`ladi.
 $y_{max} = 0$ $y_{min} = 8$ $y_{max} = 0$ $y_{min} = 8$

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